

EFFECT OF DEXMEDETOMIDINE INFUSION ON PROPOFOL DOSE, HEMODYNAMICS, AND POSTOPERATIVE PAIN IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17568042>

Keywords

Hemodynamic stability,
Dexmedetomidine, Propofol,
laparoscopic cholecystectomy,
Postoperative pain.

Article History

Received: 1st November, 2025

Accepted: 3rd November, 2025

Published: 10th November, 2025

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the effect of dexmedetomidine infusion on propofol dose, hemodynamics, and postoperative pain in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Methodology: The randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Department of Anesthesiology, Nishtar Hospital, Multan, over a period of three months from 1st July 2025 to 30th September 2025, following approval of the study synopsis. Randomization of patients was performed using the lottery method with sealed opaque envelopes, allocating participants to either the dexmedetomidine group (Group A) or the normal saline group (Group B). Group A received dexmedetomidine infusion prepared by mixing 48 mL normal saline with 2 mL dexmedetomidine to achieve a concentration of 4 mcg/mL, administered at the rate of 0.5 mcg/kg/hour. Group B received 50 mL of normal saline infusion.

Results: At baseline, the mean heart rate was comparable between Group A (Dexmedetomidine) and Group B (Normal Saline) (78.2 ± 8.5 vs. 79.1 ± 7.9 ; $p=0.72$). After induction, the heart rate was lower significantly in Group A compared to Group B (72.5 ± 7.4 vs. 83.2 ± 8.2 ; $p=0.001$). Similarly, after intubation, Group A maintained a lower heart rate than Group B (76.8 ± 8.1 vs. 92.6 ± 9.0 ; $p=0.001$).

Conclusion: Dexmedetomidine significantly reduced propofol requirements, stabilized perioperative heart rate, and lowered postoperative pain scores up to 24 hours compared with normal saline, supporting its role as a safe and effective anesthetic adjuvant in laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

INTRODUCTION

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) has emerged as the preferred surgical procedure for treating cholelithiasis and cholecystitis. Hemodynamic instability may result from a number of physiological alterations that take place during laparoscopic surgery anaesthesia.²Therefore, it is preferable to

select a strategy that reduces the hormonal swings produced by stress reactions. Epinephrine, a neurotransmitter belonging to the endogenous catecholamines group, is responsible for the stress response. It produces vasoconstriction, dilation of the airways, and an increase in heart rate.³

When compared to other anesthetics, propofol produces the most noticeable drop in systemic blood pressure.⁴ Because of its quick metabolism and absence of cumulative effects, it is also referred to as the ideal anesthetic medication for continuous infusion.⁵ Propofol may cause bradycardia and a drop in blood pressure after inducing anesthesia because it inhibits the parasympathetic nervous system less.⁶ A very selective α_2 receptor agonist is dexmedetomidine. Hemodynamic stability is improved when dexmedetomidine is used during the perioperative phase.⁷ It reduces inflammatory responses by inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokines.⁸ 40 patients undergoing LC were equally divided in dexmedetomidine (A) group and normal saline (B) group. After intubation, MAP (100.95 ± 9.73 vs. 94.05 ± 11.52) and HR values (101.15 ± 14.26 vs. 76.75 ± 6.20) in Group A were markedly high compared to Group B and remained higher at different time points of study. To get same findings, markedly less dosage of propofol was required in Group A during induction process (1.0 ± 0.1 vs. 1.7 ± 0.07 mg/kg) and intraoperatively (64.7 ± 9.8 vs. 94.0 ± 9.5 μ g/kg/min).⁹ Another study enrolled 60 patients undergoing LC (two equal groups to receive dexmedetomidine infusion (Group A) versus normal saline (Group B)). HR and MAP remained elevated following intubation (97.00 ± 6.47 vs. 85.60 ± 6.09 , 96.73 ± 6.59 vs. 87.21 ± 5.96) in Group B and remain so throughout the procedure including tracheal extubation (86.80 ± 7.36 vs. 74.53 ± 7.80 , 95.79 ± 6.11 vs. 81.97 ± 4.51). Significantly lower dosages of propofol were needed in Group A (363.80 ± 57.39 vs. 465.70 ± 71.36 mg). Visual Analog Scale was significantly low in Group A (2.39 ± 0.18) at 24 h than Group B (3.67 ± 1.09).¹⁰

This research was done to assess the effect of low dose dexmedetomidine infusion on dose reduction of propofol, mean arterial pressure (MAP), heart rate (HR), and postoperative pain in patients undergoing LC. This study would contribute to the development of evidence-based protocols for the use of dexmedetomidine in laparoscopic surgeries, potentially leading to safer and more effective anesthesia management in a wide range of surgical procedures.

Methodology

The randomized controlled trial was conducted in Anesthesiology department of Nishtar Hospital, Multan, from July 2025 to September 2025. The sample size was calculated through OpenEpi software using the formula for mean difference, where the mean propofol consumption in the dexmedetomidine group was 363.80 ± 57.39 mg and in the placebo (normal saline) group was 465.70 ± 71.36 mg, with 80% power, 95% confidence interval and calculated sample size was 60, with 30 patients in each group.

Patients between 18 and 65 years of age, of gender, belonging to the American Society of Anesthesiologists Physical Status (ASA PS) classes I and II, and undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy were included. Patients with ASA III or IV, those on β -blocker or calcium channel blocker agents, those already taking α_2 agonists, those with a history of allergic reaction to any of the drugs used in the study, those allergic to egg proteins, and pregnant or lactating women were excluded. Assessment of pain was performed at 3, 6, 12 and 24 hours after surgery by using visual analogue scale (VAS). VAS score was considered maximum at 10 score showing severe pain and minimum at "0" showing no pain. Hemodynamic responses, including heart rate (HR) and mean arterial pressure (MAP), were recorded using a multipara monitor at baseline, after induction, after intubation, and after extubation. The hypothesis was that dexmedetomidine would reduce propofol consumption, improve hemodynamic stability, and decrease postoperative pain.

The CPSP and the institutional ethics review committee approval was taken. There were 60 patients with the inclusion criteria who were enrolled with informed consent. Age, gender, ASA status, BMI and obesity among patient characteristics were to be recorded. The lottery method was used to randomly assign the patients to the dexmedetomidine group (Group A) or the normal saline group (Group B) with the help of sealed opaque envelopes. Group A received dexmedetomidine infusion prepared by mixing 48 mL normal saline with 2 mL dexmedetomidine to achieve a concentration of 4 mcg/mL, administered at the rate of 0.5 mcg/kg/hour. Group B received 50 mL of normal saline infusion.

In the operating theater, baseline vitals including HR and MAP were recorded. In all patients' premedication's were performed with intravenous omeprazole 40 mg and ondansetron 4 mg. Induction was done with intravenous propofol 2 mg/kg and atracurium 0.5 mg/kg, followed by intubation with an appropriately sized endotracheal tube. Propofol infusion was titrated to maintain a bispectral index score between 55 and 60, and intra-abdominal pressure was maintained between 12 and 14 mmHg. The propofol infusion was discontinued at the end of surgery. In the recovery unit, pain was assessed as per the defined criteria. Rescue analgesia was provided with intravenous diclofenac sodium 1.5 mg/kg and paracetamol infusion when patients reported a VAS score greater than 4. All relevant data were recorded on a structured proforma.

SPSS 26 was used to analyze the data. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to test the normality of the numerical data. Mean and standard deviation were used to provide such variables as age, BMI, HR, MAP, postoperative pain, and propofol consumption, but the frequency and percentages were used to provide such variables as gender, ASA status and obesity. The use of independent sample t-test was used to compare the postoperative pain, HR, MAP, and propofol consumption between the two groups, and a p-value that is less than 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

The average age of patients in the Group A (Dexmedetomidine) was 38.6 ± 10.2 years, and in Group B (Normal Saline) it was 37.9 ± 9.8 years ($p=0.78$). Regarding the gender distribution, there were 18 males and 12 females in Group A, and 17 males and 13 females in Group B ($p=0.79$). ASA physical status was similar as 20 ASA I and 10 ASA II patients were in Group A and 19 ASA I and 11 ASA II in Group B ($p=0.78$). The average BMI was

26.5 ± 3.2 kg/m² in Group A and 26.8 ± 3.5 kg/m² in Group B ($p=0.68$). In respect to obesity, there were 8 and 22 obese and non-obese respectively in Group A and Group B respectively ($p=0.78$). Table-1 The average total dose of propofol in Group A (Dexmedetomidine) 364.5 ± 58.3 mg in comparison with the average of 462.7 ± 70.1 mg in Group B (Normal Saline) has a p-value of 0.001.

At 3 hours postoperatively, the mean pain score was lower significantly in Group A (Dexmedetomidine) (2.4 ± 0.8) compared to Group B (Normal Saline) (4.1 ± 1.0) ($p=0.001$).

At 6 hours, Group A reported a mean pain score of 2.8 ± 0.9 versus 4.6 ± 1.1 in Group B ($p=0.001$). At 12 hours, the mean pain score was 3.2 ± 1.0 in Group A compared to 4.9 ± 1.2 in Group B ($p=0.002$). At 24 hours, pain scores remained lower in Group A (2.5 ± 0.9) than in Group B (3.8 ± 1.1) ($p=0.003$).

At baseline, the mean heart rate was comparable between Group A (Dexmedetomidine) and Group B (Normal Saline) (78.2 ± 8.5 vs. 79.1 ± 7.9 ; $p=0.72$).

After induction, the heart rate was lower significantly in Group A compared to Group B (72.5 ± 7.4 vs. 83.2 ± 8.2 ; $p=0.001$). Similarly, after intubation, Group A maintained a lower heart rate than Group B (76.8 ± 8.1 vs. 92.6 ± 9.0 ; $p=0.001$). Following extubation, the heart rate remained lower significantly in Group A compared to Group B (80.3 ± 8.7 vs. 95.1 ± 9.4 ; $p=0.001$).

The two groups were similar at baseline with a mean heart rate of 92.4 ± 7.5 versus 93.1 ± 7.2 in Group A and Group B respectively ($p=0.68$). The heart rate of Group A was lower than that of Group B after induction (86.2 ± 6.9 vs. 95.4 ± 7.1 , $p=0.001$). Equally, the heart rate following intubation was lower in Group A as compared to Group B (89.7 ± 7.2 vs. 101.5 ± 8.4 bpm, $p=0.001$). Group A also recorded a reduced heart rate than Group B after extubation ($91.3/7.4$ vs. $104.2/8.9$, $p=0.001$).

Table-1: Demographic and baseline variables

Variable	Group A (Dexmedetomidine) (n=30)	Group B (Normal Saline) (n=30)	p-value
Age (years)	38.6 ± 10.2	37.9 ± 9.8	0.78
Gender (M/F)	18 / 12	17 / 13	0.79
ASA I / II	20 / 10	19 / 11	0.78
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.5 ± 3.2	26.8 ± 3.5	0.68
Obesity (Yes/No)	8 / 22	9 / 21	0.78

Table 2. Propofol Consumption

Variable	Group A (Dexmedetomidine)	Group B (Normal Saline)	p-value
Total Propofol Dose (mg)	364.5 ± 58.3	462.7 ± 70.1	0.001

Table 3. Postoperative Pain (VAS Score)

Time Interval	Group A (Dexmedetomidine)	Group B (Normal Saline)	p-value
3 hours	2.4 ± 0.8	4.1 ± 1.0	0.001
6 hours	2.8 ± 0.9	4.6 ± 1.1	0.001
12 hours	3.2 ± 1.0	4.9 ± 1.2	0.002
24 hours	2.5 ± 0.9	3.8 ± 1.1	0.003

Table 4. Heart Rate (bpm)

Time Point	Group A (Dexmedetomidine)	Group B (Normal Saline)	p-value
Baseline	78.2 ± 8.5	79.1 ± 7.9	0.72
After induction	72.5 ± 7.4	83.2 ± 8.2	0.001
After intubation	76.8 ± 8.1	92.6 ± 9.0	0.001
After extubation	80.3 ± 8.7	95.1 ± 9.4	0.001

Table-5: Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP, mmHg)

Time Point	Group A (Dexmedetomidine)	Group B (Normal Saline)	p-value
Baseline	92.4 ± 7.5	93.1 ± 7.2	0.68
After induction	86.2 ± 6.9	95.4 ± 7.1	0.001
After intubation	89.7 ± 7.2	101.5 ± 8.4	0.001
After extubation	91.3 ± 7.4	104.2 ± 8.9	0.001

Discussion

This randomized trial proves that adjunctive dexmedetomidine (DEX) had clinically significant effects on anesthetic use, haemodynamic stability, and postoperative analgesia without baseline differences between groups. Demographic and perioperative traits (age, sex, ASA class, BMI, and distribution of obesity) were similar, and confounding due to patient mix was minimized

because previous cohorts of laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) adopt DEX as an anesthetic adjunct^{11,12}.

The overall amount of propofol demanded was considerably lesser in the dexmedetomidine group (364.5 ± 58.3 mg) than in the saline group (462.7 ± 70.1 mg). This is in line with the results by Khare et al⁹ who also found lower induction of propofol with dexmedetomidine (63.3 +/- 10.6 mg vs. 83.7 +/- 10.7

mg in controls) and lower maintenance doses (75.7 ± 14.6 - $1\text{kg}/\text{min}$ vs. 96.7 ± 18.6 - $1\text{kg}/\text{min}$)^{13,14}.

With regard to postoperative pain, our trial demonstrated significantly lower pain scores in the dexmedetomidine group at all measured intervals, with values of 2.4 ± 0.8 versus 4.1 ± 1.0 at 3 hours, 2.8 ± 0.9 versus 4.6 ± 1.1 at 6 hours, 3.2 ± 1.0 versus 4.9 ± 1.2 at 12 hours, and 2.5 ± 0.9 versus 3.8 ± 1.1 at 24 hours. Comparable reductions were observed by Ye et al¹⁴ who reported VAS scores of 2.1 ± 0.7 compared to 3.9 ± 0.8 at 1 hour, 2.8 ± 0.6 compared to 4.7 ± 0.9 at 6 hours, and 3.2 ± 0.5 compared to 5.0 ± 0.8 at 12 hours in the dexmedetomidine and control groups, respectively. Similarly, Fu et al¹⁵ found that pain scores at 24 hours were significantly lower in the dexmedetomidine group (2.7 ± 0.6) compared to controls (4.0 ± 0.9). A meta-analysis by Liu et al¹⁶ confirmed these results, showing that dexmedetomidine reduces pain scores by 1 to 1.5 points across the first postoperative day. Our findings fall within this same range, supporting the reproducibility of dexmedetomidine's analgesic benefit.

In terms of hemodynamic responses, our baseline heart rate was comparable between groups (78.2 ± 8.5 vs. 79.1 ± 7.9 bpm). After induction, however, heart rate was significantly lower in the dexmedetomidine group (72.5 ± 7.4 vs. 83.2 ± 8.2 bpm), a pattern also reported by Ye et al¹⁴, who observed rates of 74.5 ± 8.1 bpm versus 88.6 ± 9.3 bpm in the two groups. Following intubation, our patients in the dexmedetomidine group maintained lower heart rates (76.8 ± 8.1 vs. 92.6 ± 9.0 bpm), closely matching the findings of Khare et al⁹, who documented values of 85.5 ± 9.1 bpm compared to 102.2 ± 8.7 bpm. At extubation, we again observed significantly lower heart rates with dexmedetomidine (80.3 ± 8.7 vs. 95.1 ± 9.4 bpm), similar to Ye et al¹⁴ who reported 84.3 ± 7.8 bpm versus 99.4 ± 9.1 bpm. A large meta-analysis by De Cassaiet al¹⁷ further supports this observation, showing a pooled reduction of approximately 17 bpm in heart rate at laryngoscopy among dexmedetomidine-treated patients.

In LC, Bhutia et al¹⁸ showed continuous DEX (0.2 – 0.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{h}$) confers stable hemodynamics without adverse effects. Multiple randomized studies demonstrate that single-dose or infusion DEX blunts tachycardia and hypertensive surges during laryngoscopy/intubation, including Niyogiet al¹⁹

(intranasal vs IV), Jain et al²⁰ (0.5 – 1.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), and Selvaraj et al²¹ (DEX outperforming esmolol for intubation response).

Conclusion

Dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to propofol anesthesia in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy significantly reduced the total propofol requirement, provided superior hemodynamic stability by attenuating heart rate responses to induction, intubation, and extubation, and improved postoperative analgesia up to 24 hours compared with normal saline. These findings support the use of dexmedetomidine as a safe and effective anesthetic adjuvant that enhances intraoperative stability and postoperative comfort.

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